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A research project funded under the EU H2020 programme, developing enzymes for environmental-friendly products

A last word from the OXIPRO Project Coordinator, Dr. Gro Bjerga

As OXIPRO comes to a close, I find myself reflecting not only on the tangible results we've delivered but also on the lasting collaborations and fresh perspectives we've built along the way.

Our final meeting in Bergen was a fitting culmination of four years of hard work and discovery, and this last newsletter captures the energy and impact of our journey.

The main items in this issue include a detailed report from Bergen, where partners shared both their findings and ideas for what's next, and a wrap-up of our four years of work. These short reads link to longer reflections on our website, where we've also published two final news items. One highlights [our open-air campaigns](#)—creative, direct, and very much in the spirit of OXIPRO. The other celebrates [our early career researchers at NextgenBiocat](#), where they shared their innovative approaches and connected with peers across Europe.

Engaging with different stakeholders has been central to our mission, and so has supporting the next generation of enzyme researchers. Our street surveys in Bergen, lively conversations at stakeholder events, and the enthusiasm of our Early Career researchers all speak to this.

OXIPRO has never been just about lab work: it's about building bridges—between science and society, researchers and industry, regulators and innovators. And so in [this short video](#), we wrap up by summarising what enzyme technologies can do for us, and importantly, what we as a society can do to collaborate and harness these technologies for a greener and healthier environment.

Biotechnology won't solve every challenge, but we've shown it can do far more than many imagine. As this chapter closes, we'll carry forward not only the data and results but the conviction that collaboration and openness drive real change.

Finally, I would like to thank you - our stakeholders - for your support and engagement over the last four years.

OXIPRO in Bergen: A Grand Finale Celebrating Innovation, Impact and What Comes Next

As OXIPRO reached its conclusion, the consortium gathered in Bergen, Norway, from May 13–15, 2025, for a final meeting that celebrated four years of collaborative research and innovation in enzyme technology. Hosted by project coordinator NORCE, the event highlighted OXIPRO's achievements and explored pathways for future impact.

The meeting commenced with a hands-on workshop led by partner BSC, introducing participants to OXIPRO's user-friendly computational platform for enzyme discovery and engineering. This session underscored the project's commitment to accessible tools that bridge diverse scientific backgrounds.

Engaging with the public was a key feature of the Bergen gathering. Participants conducted a co-creation street survey, interacting with locals and tourists to gather insights on consumer habits and perceptions of enzyme-enabled products. This activity not only enriched OXIPRO's social awareness study but also emphasized the importance of public engagement in scientific endeavours.

Central to the meeting were presentations on OXIPRO's four innovation cases—nutraceuticals, cosmetics, detergents, and textiles. Each case demonstrated how enzyme technologies developed through the project are being applied in real-world contexts, with contributions from industry partners ensuring practical relevance and market readiness.

The Bergen meeting also featured inspirational talks from industry and policy experts, providing broader perspectives on enzyme innovation and its role in sustainable development.

For a comprehensive overview of the final meeting and its outcomes, [read the full article here](#)

Four Years in a Nutshell as OXIPRO Wraps Up

OXIPRO is a four-year initiative funded under the EU's Horizon 2020 programme and brings together a multidisciplinary team of researchers and stakeholders from 15 entities across Europe to focus on the development of novel enzymes for environment-friendly consumer products.

The OXIPRO partners have worked on developing and deploying an efficient oxidoreductase foundry using cutting-edge bioinformatics and biotechnology, and by broadening the range of industrial oxidoreductases for more sustainable processes, this initiative will ultimately contribute to the transition to environment-friendly products, with detergents, textiles, sunscreens, and nutraceuticals.

Through the integration of computational workflows and state-of-the-art biotechnological technologies, OXIPRO will expedite the lab to market journey, while shortcutting downstream implementation and ensuring market uptake. This will be supported by ecosystem intelligence generated throughout the project as well as engagement with research, policy, societal and industrial actors in co-creation and interactions to maximise output and enable faster and systemic innovations.

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To join the OXIPRO Community and receive project updates, [please register here](#)

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